

1 SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

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3 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 1. Diagnostic plots depicting studentized residuals as a function of
4 leverage for the L2 estimator applied to the example datasets shown in Figure 2 with PIC (a) and PGLS
5 (b) regression. Note that there is a single outlier (Cook's Distance > 0.5 , upper right corner) with PIC
6 regression (a), whereas there are no outliers with PGLS regression (b).

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9 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 2. Histograms illustrating distributions of RPKM values across species
 10 (rows) and tissues (columns) for male (left column within tissue) and female (right column within
 11 tissue) from the Brawand et al. (2011) dataset.

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 14 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 3. Investigating the impacts of evolutionary model violations for
 15 uncorrelated traits simulated under a shift model with variance s . Depicted are the false positive rate
 16 measured as the proportion of replicates with $P \leq 0.05$ (a-e), mean P -value (f-j), and estimate $\hat{\beta}$ of the
 17 slope coefficient β (k-o) plotted as a function of s for each of the five linear estimators (L2, M, L1, S,
 18 and MM) with PIC regression.

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 20 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 4. Investigating the impacts of evolutionary model violations for
 21 uncorrelated traits simulated under a shift model with variance s . Depicted are the false positive rate
 22 measured as the proportion of replicates with $P \leq 0.05$ (a-e), mean P -value (f-j), and estimate $\hat{\beta}$ of the
 23 slope coefficient β (k-o) plotted as a function of s for each of the five linear estimators (L2, M, L1, S,
 24 and MM) with PGLS regression.

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 26 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 5. Investigating the impacts of the degree of true trait association for
 27 correlated traits simulated with true trait covariance ρ . Depicted are the true positive rate measured as
 28 the proportion of replicates with $P \leq 0.05$ (a-e), mean P -value (f-j), and estimate $\hat{\beta}$ of the slope
 29 coefficient β (k-o) plotted as a function of ρ for each of the five linear estimators (L2, M, L1, S, and
 30 MM) with PIC regression.

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33 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 6. Investigating the impacts of the degree of true trait association for

34 correlated traits simulated with true trait covariance ρ . Depicted are the true positive rate measured as35 the proportion of replicates with $P \leq 0.05$ (a-e), mean P-value (f-j), and estimate $\hat{\beta}$ of the slope36 coefficient β (k-o) plotted as a function of ρ for each of the five linear estimators (L2, M, L1, S, and

37 MM) with PGLS regression.

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39 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 7. Phylogenetic regression in complex settings that include the joint
 40 scenario of a shift s and nonzero trait covariance $\rho \in \{0.1, 0.25, 0.50\}$ with $m = 256$ species. Rows
 41 depict results for the three values $\rho \in \{0.1, 0.25, 0.50\}$, and columns depict true positive rates (a-c),
 42 estimates of the regression coefficient (d-f), and standard deviations of coefficient estimates (g-i).

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45 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 8. Exploring robust regression for predicting female expression as a
 46 function of male expression in three tissues from nine species. Distributions of P -value for each of the
 47 five estimators (L2, M, L1, S, and MM; a-c), ΔP -value (difference between P -values of each robust
 48 estimator and the L2 estimator; d-f), and $\Delta\hat{\beta}$ (difference between coefficient estimates of each robust
 49 estimator and the L2 estimator; g-i) with PIC regression applied to expression data from 5,615 genes
 50 in heart (top row), kidney (center row), and brain (bottom row) tissues. Outliers have been removed
 51 from boxplots to better visualize major differences among distributions.

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54 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 9. Alluvial plots showing relative fractions of genes with significant (P
 55 ≤ 0.05) and non-significant ($P > 0.05$) correlated expression in female and male brain, heart, and kidney
 56 tissues from nine species. Depicted are inferences from the standard L2 estimator (left side of each
 57 panel) compared with M (a), L1 (b), S (c), and MM (d) estimators with PIC regression. For example,
 58 in panel (a), the fraction of non-significant genes with both L2 and M estimation are shown at the top,
 59 while significant genes with L2 and non-significant genes with M estimation result in mismatched
 60 connections.

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64 SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 10. Applying robust phylogenetic regression to muscle fiber data from
 65 22 lizard species. Shown is the predicted relationship between the proportion of slow glycolytic fibers
 66 and the proportion of fast oxidative fibers for regression using the L2 (black), M (blue), L1 (purple), S
 67 (orange), and MM (red) estimators. The black arrow denotes a single high-leverage outlier point that
 68 leads the L2, M, and L1 estimators to not identify the negative association between the two traits.